

THE EFFECTS OF HYGROTHERMAL ENVIRONMENT ON THE
ALUMINUM/CARBON(GRAPHITE) FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A number of studies on the behaviours of aluminum/carbon(graphite) composite wires after exposure to the hygrothermal environment have been carried out. It is indicated that the water(moisture) penetrating into the composites would cause the weight gain, hydrolysis of aluminum carbide and dissolve of aluminum matrix, which would lead to the weakening of interface bond and variation of tensile strength. It is harmful to behaviours of composite wires in hygrothermal environment when a large amount of aluminum carbide exists. Therefore, it is suggested that the considerations of preventing a large amount of aluminum carbide formation or some protective coatings are very necessary.

INTRODUCTION

It is important to observe the behaviours of aluminum/carbon(graphite) composites after exposed to the hygrothermal environment. Since in this case, water(moisture) should attack the easily hydrolytic interfacial reaction product - aluminum carbide(Al_4C_3) formed in fabrication processes or after evaluated temperature exposure. In addition, the existance of water with electrolytes provides galvanic coupling effects between carbon fibers and aluminum matrix.

The effects of some environment mediums on aluminum/graphite composite materials have been studied. Dull et al. [1] have found that the weight of Al/Gr composites increases after exposed to 3.5% NaCl solution, which is attributed to the formation of galvanic corrosion product, does not increase in distilled water. The pitting, in some instances, exfoliation were observed from the Al/Gr composites after exposed to marine environment [2].

In this paper, the behaviours of four kinds of carbon(graphite) fiber reinforced aluminum alloy composite wires were investigated after exposure to the hygrothermal environment, including the weight gain by take-up water, variation of aluminum carbide content by hydrolysis, changing of the fraction of aluminum matrix by galvanic corrosion and influence on the tensile strength. The emphasis of this paper was concentrated on the effects of aluminum carbide existence on the behaviours of composites in the hygrothermal environment. It is anticipated that the experimental results would give some ideas in the selection of matrix compositions, fabrication techniques and adopt measures to prevent interfacial corrosion, and the more understanding on the effects of aluminum carbide on composites would also be obtained.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Four kinds of carbon(graphite) fiber reinforced aluminum alloy composite wires(approximately 0.5 mm in diameter) which are fabricated in our laboratory by means of the method of chemical vapour deposition to form Ti-B coating on the fibers and then infiltrating with Al-Si(10%) alloy and LD2(forging aluminum alloy), were used in this study. The main compositions of LD2 are Si 1.04%, Mg 0.65%, Cu 0.45%, Mn 0.28%. The fibers are carbon fiber(Cs) made in shanghai Carbon Work Factory, China and graphite fiber(M40) made in Toray, Japan. The part of composite wires exposure to environment were as-received(case A), and the others were treated at 700°C(973 K) for 15 minutes in vaccum(approximately 10^{-3} Torr) before exposure, which was to produce a large amount of aluminum carbide (case B). All of the specimens were divided into four groups and then put in a commercial type hygro-thermo regulator(Model DL-302, made in China). Each group was taken out for testing at about 10 days interval. After that, the weight, Al_4C_3 content, matrix fraction(wt.%) and tensile strength of specimens were measured by various techniques.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. Weight Gain of the Composite Wires

One of the significant changes for composite wires after exposure to the hygrothermal environment is weight gain which is attributed to water absorbed. Figure 1 shows the weight of composite wires as a function of exposure time. A general increase in weight of composite wires for both

cases is evident. It is obvious that weight gain for case B is much greater than case A. Taking the slope on the weight versus time plot, we can get the curves of weight gain rate, that is, water absorbed rate as a function of exposure time, as given in Figure 2. It shows two contrary tendencies, the rate decreases drastically with exposure going on for case B and increases gradually for case A. The difference of two cases is

Figure 1. Weight gain of the composite wires a) case A; b) case B after exposure to the hygrothermal environment.

Figure 2. Weight gain rate of composite wires after exposure to the hygrothermal environment.

probably attributed to the existence of a large amount of aluminum carbide in the composite wires. The thermal exposure to evaluated temperature has made a great difference in content of aluminum carbide between two cases, as given in Table 1. We can see the maximum exceeding 1×10^5 ppm for LD2/M40 after exposure(case B).

TABLE 1

The Original Content of Al_4C_3 of composite wires for both cases (ppm)

Case	Al-Si/M40	LD2/M40	Al-Si/Cs	LD2/Cs
A	1484	1526	11983	13695
B	89733	119789	44467	28817

II. The Hydrolysis of Aluminum Carbide and Dissolve of Aluminum Matrix

The water penetrating into the composites would cause the hydrolysis of Al_4C_3 and dissolve of aluminum matrix.

Al_4C_3 hydrolyzes easily when it meets water, as followed [3],

From the results of x-ray diffraction, we found that the diffraction peaks of Al_4C_3 disappear completely after exposure, which means the Al_4C_3 have hydrolyzed. This is also confirmed by the results from the gas chromatograph measurement. The results are given in Figure 3. It is

Figure 3. Aluminum carbide content as a function of exposure time. case A (hollow), case B (solid).

evident that the content of Al_4C_3 subsides with exposure time, and the higher the original content of Al_4C_3 , the faster the content of Al_4C_3 decreasing. For example, the content of Al_4C_3 for case B decreases much than case A, especially for graphite fiber reinforced Al composites, and for graphite fiber reinforced Al composites, decreases greater than carbon fiber reinforced Al composites in case B, because of higher original content of aluminum carbide.

Since the standard electrical potential of aluminum is negative, once electrolyte solution exists, the corrosion cell would be formed between carbon fiber and aluminum matrix, which would lead to dissolve of aluminum matrix. When the composites expose to hygrothermal environment, a layer of water solution with some electrolytes taking from the environment such as CO_2 would be formed on surfaces of the composites. Thus, this water solution penetrates into the capillaries along interface and surface defects of the composites, then a galvanic couple of aluminum-carbon between fibers and matrix is formed and aluminum matrix would dissolve as anode with the hydrate of aluminum as product of dissolving process. The fraction(wt.%) of aluminum matrix of some specimens is determined by means of differential scanning calorimetry(DSC) method, as shown in Table 2. It is obvious that the appreciable decrease is occurred.

TABLE 2
The fraction of aluminum matrix(wt.%) after exposure to the
hygrothermal environment

Specimen	Case	Exposure time (days)				
		0	10	16	20	38
Al-Si/M40	A	60	-	-	-	52
	B	56	46	-	-	39
LD2/M40	B	34	19	-	(22)	14

The effects of hydrolysis of Al_4C_3 and dissolve of aluminum matrix on weight gain rate(water absorbed rate) are different, which lead to two tendencies of weight gain rate for two cases.

In the instance of no other active corrosion passages(such as no or less Al_4C_3 content), such as case A, the existance of protective oxide film on surface of aluminum would block the galvanic corrosion occurring before it damaged. Water penetrates into composites in case of the crevices

extending deeper in it. The crevices are attributed to the formation of corrosion product $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, which have higher specific volume than aluminum matrix. Thus, the internal stress caused by the volume effect is formed in the composites, especially at the interface, and then crevices take place at the meanwhile. In fact, we have observed the crevices from the transverse sections of composite wires by means of SEM, as shown in Figure 4. It is clear that water penetrating rate (or water absorbed rate) is related closely to the corrosion rate of aluminum matrix. Since oxide film

Figure 4. Scanning Electron Micrograph of the crevices formed on Al-Si/M40 composites(case A) after exposure to the hygrothermal environment.

must be damaged at first, so that the water take-up is initially smaller and then increases gradually with exposure time. However, due to the limiting of aluminum corrosion rate, the water absorbed rate is lower. In addition, the granular appearance on the surfaces of composite wires is observed in this case, as shown in Figure 5.

When a large amount of aluminum carbide which is an active passage exists in composites, such as case B, the water would heavily penetrate into it accompanying with hydrolysis of Al_4C_3 , water absorbed rate is higher. However, the water absorbed rate would decrease followed by the decrease of Al_4C_3 content. In this case, we found some cracks crossing longitudinally along whole composite wires. One of the cracks observed by SEM is shown in Figure 6. In addition, we have also observed that most of composite wires are swelling, and the color of surfaces apparently turns from silvery white to deep grey or black.

Figure 5. Morphology of surfaces of LD2/M40 composite wires
a) as-received; b) after 38 days exposure to the
hygrothermal environment.

Figure 6. Morphology of crack formed on surfaces of LD2/M40
composite wires (case B) after exposure to the
hygrothermal environment.

It is considered that the water absorbed rate is primarily controlled by dissolve of matrix for case A since the content of Al_4C_3 is smaller, and by hydrolysis of Al_4C_3 for case B in which a large amount of Al_4C_3 exists. This is the reason why two tendencies of water absorbed rate are different shown as above. In fact, fresh matrix would be exposed as the Al_4C_3 hydrolyzes, which might increase the water take-up and speed up the

the dissolve of matrix. Therefore, the dissolve of matrix for case B is more serious than case A.

Portnoi, et al. [4] have indicated that the weight gain may be as a criterion for corrosion resistance of composites. Thus, it is obvious that existance of aluminum carbide is detrimental to corrosion resistance, so that the approaches of preventing massive Al_4C_3 formation and some protective coatings must be considered for use in higher relative humidity condition.

III. The Effects on the Tensile Strength

It is well known that the tensile strength of composites is related to interface bonding. Thus, the variations of interface bonding inevitably cause the variations of tensile strength. The formation of aluminum carbide would strengthen the bonding of interface [5] and would lead to weakening of interface bonding when hydrolysis occurs. The formation of crevices in composites, particularly at interface caused by dissolve of aluminum matrix, weaken the interface bonding further. Moreover, the corrosion products also change the ability of loading-transfer of the matrix. All of these effects lead to the tensile strength variation. Figure 7 shows the tensile strength as a function of exposure time.

The Composite Wires for case A For specimens Al-Si/M40, LD2/Cs(Figure 7) the tensile strength tends to variation in a similar way which is in a gradual degradation form, and for specimens Al-Si/Cs, LD2/M40(Figure 7), tends to another similar way, that is, slight increase at the initial stage and then followed by decrease and keep no or less change at the last duration during exposure processes. These phenomena just coincide with the results obtained in the thermal cycling studies [6]. The penetrating passages limited, the weakening of interface is not uniform, therefore, the extent of variation of tensile strength are much smaller than in case of thermal cycling.

The two tendencies of tensile strength shown after exposure to hydrothermal environment might be connected with the original interface bonding state as we have discussed in the reference[6] for instance of thermal cycling experiment. It is indicated that, with the further weakening of interface bonding, the tensile strength decreases if the original interface bonding is lower than optimal state and increases, then decreases if the original strength is stronger than the optimal state.

Figure 7. Variation of tensile strength of composite wires (— case A, ---- case B) after exposure to the hygrothermal environment.

It must be noted that the effects of corrosion product on tensile strength can not be ignore.

The Composite Wires for case B The tensile strength tends to degradation for Al-Si/M40 and LD2/M40, slightly increases and then decreases for Al-Si/Cs and LD2/Cs after exposure. Because massive matrix has been attacked in a very serious form, so that further discussion is unnecessary.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Under the condition of temperature 70°C, relative humidity 95%, the hydrolysis of Al_4C_3 and dissolve of matrix occurs. The content of Al_4C_3 and matrix(wt.%) obviously decreases after exposure.
2. Weight of composite wires increases. The existance of Al_4C_3 have an obvious effects on weight gain and its rate.
3. The tensile strength changes apparently after exposure to hygrothermal environment.
4. Some measures must be considered to prevent the large amount of Al_4C_3

formation to enhance the corrosion resistance, and certain protective coatings must also be considered for use under higher relative humidity conditions.

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